

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**KNOWLEDGE REGARDING COMMON RISK FACTORS OF
ORAL CANCER AT DHQ HOSPITAL MIRPUR AJK**

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Article Received: April 2019

Accepted: May 2019

Published: June 2019

Abstract:

Background: Oral cancer is one of the life-threatening conditions in world early diagnosis can increase the chance of survival. Lack of public awareness is the potent barrier factor for early detection. Study was carried out to see knowledge of common risk factors of oral cancer among adult patients visiting DHQ Hospital Mirpur AJK.

Material Methods: Self-administered proforma containing 10 questions were distributed among 120 patients age group 18 to 28. Study carried out at DHQ Hospital Mirpur AJK. Our study duration is from Jun 2016 to August 2016. Data was analyzed using SPSS 16.

Results: Out of 120 patients 90 were male and 30 were female. Results showed adults population visiting DHQ hospital Mirpur having good knowledge regarding risk factors of oral cancer.

Conclusion: Despite of having good knowledge regarding risk factors of oral cancer a huge amount of adult population used to it. Government should take steps in order to ban these harmful products.

Key Words: Knowledge, Oral cancer, Risk factors.

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Please cite this article in press Zara Javed et al., *Knowledge Regarding Common Risk Factors Of Oral Cancer At Dhq Hospital Mirpur Ajk., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06[06].*

INTRODUCTION:

Each year 4,50,000 patients were diagnosed with oral cancer worldwide. In last decades researchers have found an increase in incidence in young patients especially with cancer involving tongue (1). Oral cancer can occur anywhere i.e. tongue, gingiva, lips, mouth and throat. Bleeding and non-healing ulcers in oral cavity is the common feature of oral cancer (2). The major risk factors for oral cancer has been established by various studies including smoking, alcohol consumption and betel liquid chewing (3).80% cases diagnosed at localized stage and 30% have tendency to metalize to other sites. (4)

Lack of knowledge about oral cancer is the leading case of oral cancer. In different countries cancer programs held but there more emphasis on other

cancers like Breast ,Prostate, Cervical brain metises(5).

MATERIAL MATHODS:

Study was carried out among patients visiting at DHQ Hospital Mirpur AJK from Jun 2016 to August 2016. Study was conducted among 120 patients. Sample technique was non -probability(convenience) and study design was Descriptive cross sectional. Patients age group from 18 to 28 years were included in the study. Proforma was designed for assessment of knowledge of common risk factors of oral cancer. Data was analyzed using SPSS 16.

RESULTS:

Knowledge regarding risk factors of oral cancer were assessed among 120 patients to which 90(75%) were male and 30(25%) were female.

Table 1: Age and Gender distribution of Patients:

Age Groups	Male	Female	Percentage
18-20	16	4	16.6%
21-22	30	8	31.6%
23-23	18	6	20%
24-26	10	8	15%
27-28	6	14	16.6%
Total	80	40	100%

Table 2: Showing knowledge regarding oral cancer Risk factors.

Knowledge Regarding	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
Smoking	40	10	50	41.6%
Alcohol	16	8	24	20%
Pan	34	12	46	38.3%
Total	90	30	120	100%

Study shows adult population of Mirpur AJK know about risk factors causing oral cancer.41.6% know oral cancer due to smoking while 38.3% know that oral cancer due to Pan.

Table 3: Showing Hobbits among Participants.

Hobbits	Male	Female	Percentage
Smoking	48	12	50%
Alcohol	13	0	10.8%
Pan	29	18	39.1%
Total	90	30	100%

Regarding hobbits 50 participants are smoker among them 48 were male and 12 were female. None of female involved in alcohol intake.

DISCUSSION:

Oral cancer is the life-threatening condition and is the 11th most common disease in the world. Early diagnosis can prevent its outcomes (6).

Results of our study shows similarity with study conducted by Islamic international dental hospital Islamabad in 2011. Their study showed people of Islamabad has good knowledge regarding risk factors of oral cancer with overall of 54% awareness rate. (7) A prospective study by Maserejian et al showed alcohol consumption is consistently related to higher risk of oral cancer, 26% of respondents consumes alcohol only (8). Another study at north central Wisconsin showed people having very good knowledge about oral cancer risk factors.

Although people of Mirpur also have good knowledge regarding harmful effects of oral cancer, but they are using these products as they are addicted to them.

CONCLUSION:

As patient's despite of having good knowledge of risk factors of oral cancer they are used to it. Government should ban these harmful products where they are extremely used.

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